

and 1.46 B.M., respectively (Table 1). It appears from the result that the salt and both the varieties of mononuclear complex contain quinquivalent molybdenum having d^1 configurations. The ir spectrum of the salt, $\text{PymbzH}_2[\text{MoOCl}_5]$ shows a strong band at 980 cm^{-1} while for both the varieties of non-electrolyte it appears at 975 cm^{-1} . These bands can be assigned to the terminal $\text{Mo}=\text{O}$ vibration⁵. The lowering of stretching frequencies by 5 cm^{-1} , from salt to non-electrolyte, may probably be due to the strong donating capabilities of the nitrogen atom of the ligand and thus causing increased electron density around the central metal atom and reducing its π -acceptance capacity and ultimately the metal oxygen bond strength.

The uv and visible spectra of the salt were recorded in 12 M HCl while for the other in acetonitrile medium. The observed results clearly agree with the previous observation^{6,7}.

The salt, 2(2'-pyridyl) benzimidazoliumoxopentachloromolybdate(V) in 12 M HCl shows two crystal field transitions around $14000\text{ (}^2\text{B}_2 \rightarrow ^2\text{E(I))}$ and $22000\text{ cm}^{-1}\text{ (}^2\text{B}_2 \rightarrow ^2\text{B}_1)$, and three charge transfer transitions around $27000\text{ (}^2\text{B}_2 \rightarrow ^2\text{E(II))}$, $34000\text{ (}^2\text{B}_2 \rightarrow ^2\text{B}_2\text{(I))}$ and $43000\text{ cm}^{-1}\text{ (}^2\text{B}_2 \rightarrow ^2\text{E(III))}$, respectively. Similarly, for both the varieties of non-electrolyte the bands appear around 13000 , 19000 , 27000 , 33000 and 42000 cm^{-1} which may be assigned to the transitions, $^2\text{B}_2 \rightarrow ^2\text{E(I)}$, $\text{L} \rightarrow \text{Mo}$ charge transfer, $^2\text{B}_2 \rightarrow ^2\text{B}_1$, $^2\text{B}_2 \rightarrow ^2\text{B}_2\text{(I)}$ and $^2\text{B}_2 \rightarrow ^2\text{E(III)}$, respectively.

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Oxovanadium(IV) and Dioxouranium(VI) Complexes with Dioxime of Fluorene Glyoxal

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OF many oxo metal species studied, VO^{2+} and UO_2^{2+} are the most stable^{1,2}. Both the ions form various types of stable complexes with different ligands. The complexes of VO^{2+}

with macrocyclic ligands³ derived from 2,6-dipicolinoaldihydrazine and β -diketones have been studied. The electron spin resonance studies on dihalogenovanadium(IV) having different ground states are some recent revelations⁴.

The complexes of dioxouranium(VI) with many monobasic bidentate and dibasic tetradentate Schiff bases have been studied recently⁵ and many interesting features pertaining to their physico-chemical aspects have been divulged. Aforesaid investigations led to synthesise a new ligand and its complexes with oxovanadium(IV) and dioxouranium(VI) ions. In the present investigation we have isolated oxovanadium(IV) and dioxouranium(VI) complexes of fluorene glyoxal dioxime and characterised them with the help of elemental analysis, magnetic moment, ir and electronic spectral data.

Experimental

All the reagents used were of A.R. grade and the solvents were purified by distillation.

Preparation of ligand: Fluorene glyoxal was obtained from fluorene by its acetylation and subsequent oxidation by selenium dioxide⁶.

Dioxime of fluorene glyoxal was prepared by refluxing hydroxylamine hydrochloride and fluorene glyoxal in molar ratio of 2 : 1 in an aqueous NaOH solution for about 30 min. After cooling in ice-bath, 2-3 ml of water was added to get brownish black precipitate. After washing with water it was recrystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 160°).

Preparation of complexes: Oxovanadyl(IV) complex was prepared by refluxing aqueous ethanolic solutions of vanadyl chloride and ligand in molar ratio of 1 : 2. The green precipitate thus obtained was filtered and washed with aqueous ethanol and finally dried at 120° .

Dioxouranium(VI) complex was prepared by mixing ethanolic solution of dioxime with uranyl iodide solution in ethanol. Uranyl iodide was prepared by methathesis (addition of KI to uranyl acetate). The yellow crystalline complex separated out was filtered, washed with ethanol and dried.

Infrared spectra (KBr) were recorded on Beckman and Unicam SP 1200 spectrophotometer at Department of Chemistry, Delhi University, and Textile and Chemistry Department, I.I.T., New Delhi. The magnetic measurements were carried out at room temperature on Gouy balance. Electronic spectra in solution were recorded on Bausch and Lomb Spectronic-20 spectrophotometer. Carbon and hydrogen were estimated by microanalytical methods. Nitrogen was determined by Kjeldahl's method, vanadium and uranium by conventional gravimetric methods (Table 1).

Results and Discussion

The ligand was found to be brownish black in colour and stable. It showed bidentate nature in all the complexes. In oxovanadium(IV) complex

TABLE I—ELEMENTAL ANALYSIS OF LIGAND AND OXOVANADIUM(IV) AND DIOXOURANIUM(VI) COMPLEXES

Compound	Colour	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				
		Metal	C	H	N	I
(C ₁₅ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂)	Brownish black	—	66.50 (64.86)	5.50 (5.41)	19.21 (18.61)	—
[VO(C ₁₅ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂)H ₂ O]	Green	8.34 (8.68)	62.89 (61.32)	3.81 (4.08)	9.34 (9.54)	—
[UO ₂ (C ₁₅ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂)I ₂]	Dark yellow	22.20 (23.19)	35.89 (35.08)	2.09 (2.14)	5.33 (5.45)	24.19 (24.75)

the ligand is deprotonated and in dioxouranium(VI) complex no deprotonation of ligand takes place. Complexes are stable in air and are formed in 1 : 2 metal ligand stoichiometry.

The normal temperature magnetic moment value of oxovanadium(IV) complex lies in the range 1.73-1.75 B.M. while the complex of dioxouranium(VI) shows diamagnetic nature. In d¹ oxovanadium(IV) complex orbital contribution is almost quenched and the spin orbital coupling constant is positive, therefore, the complex exhibits magnetic moment around 1.75 B.M.^{1,7}, which is well in the range of oxovanadium(IV) complex having symmetry lower than octahedral. This value also suggests that there is no significant antiferromagnetic interactions between pairs of oxovanadium(IV) ions in the complex in solid state. The oxovanadium complex exhibits d-d bands at around 12500, 17600 and 22300 cm⁻¹, possibly due to transitions^{2,10} d_{xy} → d_{yz}, d_{zx}; d_{xy} → d_{x²-y²} and d_{xy} → d_{z²}, indicating distorted octahedral geometry, elongation being xy plane. But in the present case, the distinction made between axial and equatorial parameters D_s and D_t, respectively indicates the difference in bond length of axial and equatorial bond lengths. The evaluation of these parameters suggests elongation along z-axis, hence, the energy level scheme suggested by Selbin cannot be applied. The scheme proposed by Lever⁹ very well explains such distortion.

Therefore, the observed transitions may be assigned as :

$$125000 \text{ cm}^{-1} \nu [e_g \rightarrow b_{2g}] \quad (1)$$

$$17600 \text{ cm}^{-1} \nu [e_g \rightarrow a_{1g}] \quad (2)$$

$$22300 \text{ cm}^{-1} \nu [e_g \rightarrow b_{1g}] \quad (3)$$

The magnetic and electronic spectral findings on complexes [VO(L)H₂O] of tetradentate macroligands derived from 2,6-dipicolinoyl dihydrazine and β-diketones have also been reported recently which lend enough support to our interpretations⁸.

Analogous to many dioxouranium(VI) complexes⁹ of bidentate and tetradentate Schiff base, [UO₂X₂(L₂)] and [UO₂X₂L], respectively, the present complex has been found to have [UO₂(C₁₅H₁₁N₂O₂)₂I₂] composition. Conductivity measurements indicate that the complex is non-electrolyte. The magnetic measurements show that the complex is diamagnetic. It shows electronic spectral band at 23000 cm⁻¹ suggesting the equatorial ligation as it has influenced the spectrum of uranyl ion. This band is assigned to charge transfer E_g¹⁺ → ³v, and is lower in range than free uranyl ion¹⁰.

In the dioxouranium(VI) complex, the ir frequency at 320 cm⁻¹ is assigned to U—I band¹¹. The metal-nitrogen bands have been reported to occur in the region 600-500 cm⁻¹ for a number of complexes¹². An intense band in the region 560-530 cm⁻¹ is assigned to M—N vibrations in the present complexes. The ir spectrum of ligand under study shows bands at 3500 (NOH), 1630 (C=N) and 1240 cm⁻¹ (N—O) stretchings. The position of N—O band shifts to higher frequency suggesting coordination through nitrogen atoms of dioxime, however, an insignificant change in ν_{C=N} in the complex is probably on account of strong force existing in C=N group. Similar observations have been made by other workers¹².

In the oxovanadium(IV) complex, the loss of water, relatively at higher temperature (> 150°) indicates that water is coordinated and not lattice-held.

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Metal Derivatives of Antimony Thiocarboxylates. Part-IV. Complexes of Silver(I), Aluminium(III), Chromium(III), Iron(III), O-Zirconium(IV) and Thorium(IV) with Antimony Hydrogen Bis(thiolactate)

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IN continuation to our studies on metal derivatives of antimony hydrogen bis-(thioglycollate) and -(thiolactate)^{1,2} we report here the syntheses and structural studies of the complexes of antimony hydrogen bis(thiolactate) with Ag^I, Al^{III}, Cr^{III}, Fe^{III}, OZr^{IV} and Th^{IV}. Formation constant studies of Al^{III} and Cr^{III} complexes in aqueous medium have also been made.

Experimental

Materials: All the chemicals used were chemically pure. The ligand, antimony hydrogen bis(thiolactate) was prepared and purified by known methods^{3,4}.

Aluminium(III), chromium(III) and iron(III) sulphates (Merck, Pure), Ag^I, Zr^{IV} and Th^{IV} nitrates (B.D.H., Pure) solutions were used after analysis.

Preparation of complexes: To a solution of the ligand antimony hydrogen bis(thiolactate) in hot water, the required amount of aqueous metal ion solution was added depending upon the ratio in which the reaction was to be carried out. An

immediate precipitation of the complex occurred except for aluminium and chromium. The reaction mixture was allowed to stand for some time for complete precipitation. The solid product was then filtered, washed with hot water and hot ethanol, and dried under reduced pressure (2 mm) at 50°.

In case of aluminium and chromium complexes, the precipitation was carried out by adding NaOH solution (0.1 N). Metals in the compounds were estimated by the known methods and the results are given in Table 1 along with other data.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Complex	Colour	Analysis % : Found/Calcd.		
		Metal	C	H
Ag(C ₆ H ₆ O ₄ S ₂ Sb)	White	23.86 (24.65)	15.82 (16.45)	1.78 (1.83)
Al(C ₆ H ₆ O ₄ S ₂ Sb) ₃	White	2.31 (2.65)	20.04 (21.25)	2.24 (2.36)
Cr(C ₆ H ₆ O ₄ S ₂ Sb) ₃	Bluish green	4.62 (5.00)	20.12 (20.74)	2.18 (2.30)
Fe(C ₆ H ₆ O ₄ S ₂ Sb) ₃	Dark brown	5.02 (5.34)	20.21 (20.66)	2.38 (2.30)
OZr(C ₆ H ₆ O ₄ S ₂ Sb) ₃	White	11.42 (11.90)	18.41 (18.78)	2.01 (2.09)
Th(C ₆ H ₆ O ₄ S ₂ Sb) ₄	White	14.10 (14.96)	17.93 (18.57)	1.94 (2.06)

Physical measurements: Ir spectra (nujol) were recorded on Beckman IR-20 spectrophotometer. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were carried out on Gouy balance. The diffused reflectance spectra were recorded on SP700 spectrophotometer. pH was measured with a Philips PR 9405M pH meter with glass and calomel electrodes assembly. The instrument was calibrated using buffer tablets of pH 4 and 9.2.

Results and Discussion

The ligand, antimony hydrogen bis(thiolactate) was prepared as reported earlier³⁻⁵.

In the ir spectrum of thioacetic acid the carbonyl stretching vibrations (ν_{as} and ν_s) were observed at 1715 and 1680 cm⁻¹. These bands shifted to 1625 and 1450 cm⁻¹, respectively on the formation of organoantimony compounds, which further shifted to lower frequency in the ranges of 1570-1550 and 1400-1370 cm⁻¹ on complex formation with different metals as observed in their ir spectra. These lowerings suggest that COO⁻ acted as a bidentate bridging chelating ligand⁶ and is consistent with the results obtained in case of CaCu(OAc)₄.6H₂O⁷. The zirconium complex showed a sharp band at 870 cm⁻¹ (Zr—O)⁸.

Magnetic moments of Cr^{III} complex (4.14 B.M.) was consistent with the octahedral structure having d³ system¹, whereas electronic spectrum of Cr^{III} complex showed bands at 700, 490 and 380 nm as expected for octahedral coordination⁹.

The trivalent iron complex was found to have magnetic moment of 3.68 B.M., a value less than that